

EVERY PESO COUNTS

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My thoughts on during my childhood years are vivid. My parents would always store five- or ten-peso coins in a coin bank. Back then, it seemed like a usual activity; however, I found myself surprise with how those pennies became substantial in time. The simple act my parents have shown taught me a very important lesson: Wealth comes not through shortcuts but through consistency and discipline. I started saving in college, and to date, it has become part of my routine.

To me, saving is psychological. Saving entails much more than putting away some money in a savings account. Rather, saving involves building the right attitude towards one's financial dealings. Some think that one cannot save unless they are earning a lot of money; nevertheless, saving begins when one decides to make use of their financial resources properly. With this attitude, individuals are more willing to save, knowing that every penny is an investment in their future success. People should know they need to save, regardless of their salary or income. According to some financial experts, such as Robert Kiyosaki and Chinkee Tan, automating savings is highly recommended. Automated saving includes practices such as salary deductions. In fact, based on my experience, it works very well because when one has set aside a particular amount of money before receiving his net salary, he will not find saving a burden. Hence, the principle of 'Savings before Spending' is followed.

Saving requires consistency, too. My parents were able to accumulate a large amount of money from the small coins they would drop into their coin banks every day. In fact, saving has nothing to do with one's income. It depends on the individual's discipline and willingness to save regularly, no matter the source of income. Whether it is a monthly allowance, salary, or income from other sources, consistent saving is very useful.

The lessons I have learned from my parents about saving and being financially responsible remain applicable to this day. Saving has nothing to do with how much money a person earns. Instead, saving involves one's willingness to set aside money regularly.

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